

PRACTICAL AND THEORETICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF MEDIA LITERACY IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM (PRIMARY EDUCATION)

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Abstract: In this article discusses the use of media techniques and the scientific theoretical importance of media literacy in the educational system, especially in primary education.

Key words: Educational system, media literacy, primary education, methodology, practical activity, information technology.

Media and information literacy is a set of knowledge, skills, attitudes, skills and practices that enable the effective acquisition, analysis, critical evaluation, interpretation, use, creation and distribution of information and media products using all necessary tools in creative activities. Today, the ability to select and correctly evaluate information remains relevant in the world mass media. Media literacy, media education, media culture, resistance to fake and propaganda information - all these key words reflected the essence of the two-day seminar training. "What is media literacy and how should it be taught at school?" as part of the project "Introduction of media literacy into the educational system of Uzbekistan". This seminar-training on the topic was organized in cooperation with the Center for the Development of Modern Journalism of Uzbekistan, DW Academy and the German side. During the training, the participants exchanged ideas with their experiences, received news such as the "Language of Justice", content, Vebler scheme, various information, methods and methodologies¹.

Why is it increasingly important today? The multifold acceleration of the flow of information, the increase of positive information as well as negative information made it necessary to acquire media literacy. Traditionally, media literacy consisted of a person's ability to analyze literary texts and create quality texts. Today, media literacy means knowing how and why information is being transmitted. Who created this information for a media literate person and for what purpose? Is this message necessary for me? He should be able to ask the question and draw a correct conclusion, and have a critical approach to it. These questions should be asked not only when you are watching TV with your family, listening to the radio in the car or watching the news on the Internet, but also when receiving and evaluating information. Media literacy is critical to understanding today's news environment. So, why is media literacy necessary? First of all:

- *To understand the essence of the reforms implemented as a full-fledged, active citizen of our legal democratic society;*
- *Formation of skills to sort the daily information transmitted and received through mass media;*

¹ Информационные и коммуникационные технологии в образовании / Под ред. Б. Дендева. М.: ИИТО ЮНЕСКО, 2013. — 320 с.

- *To avoid controlling the human mind through information and to make the right decision in any situation;*
- *To be able to analyze positive or negative changes of a person under the influence of visual images and to "read" invisible information given under visual messages;*
- *Analyzing the nature of textual communications given through mass media;*

It is necessary to find answers to the questions of where, by whom and for what purposes the information is being transmitted, whose interests it reflects. There are different opinions about the concept of media literacy, and it is noted in the American International Encyclopedia of Society that "Media literacy is the ability of a person to be active and literate while feeling his responsibility as a citizen in society, to be able to receive and create media texts, it means to be able to analyze and evaluate, to be able to understand the socio-cultural and political content of modern media". The goal of media literacy is to form the ability to sort out the information disseminated by them while understanding the priorities and shortcomings of each media, and to form the skills to accept what is necessary, while the main task is to limit it, realizing the manipulative power of any information consumed by people. It is also to help people understand the role of media and citizen journalism.

In our opinion, media literacy is an integral part of media education. At the same time, its appearances are increasing. Today, the concepts entering our language as a result of media analysis, i.e., media literacy, media education, media study, etc., are related to each other, but media is the process of receiving, sorting, and analyzing information. together with the concept of media literacy, the concepts of media education, media learning, and media culture are used in the assessment. For example:

- media is integrated in the curriculum, subjects are studied on the basis of aro;
- to analyze the "media subject" within a specific discipline;
- a critical approach to the media through practice and analysis;
- to study its form, technologies, methods of information transmission;
- to study media agencies, their social, political and cultural role;
- the student's communication with the mass media;
- research activities;
- studies the influence of the media on the audience through language and art.

Media studies in turn:

- *theoretical study of media;*
- *comparative analysis of the media;*
- *its conceptual structure;*
- *analysis of media text and methods of its creation;*
- *interdependence of mass communication, cinematography and cultural sciences;*
- *He studies the influence of mass media.*

Media literacy is the study of media and is based on the following outcomes of media education and aims to:

- ❖ *understanding the impact of media on individuals and society;*
- ❖ *understanding of mass communication process;*
- ❖ *ability to understand and analyze media texts;*
- ❖ *understanding the media context;*
- ❖ *creating media texts and analyzing them;*
- ❖ *the media sets the tasks of evaluating texts and sorting them.*

Today's media, i.e. mass media, cinema, theater, types of art, cultural influences, any information transmitted through the Internet has a certain effect on a person and changes his worldview. causing change. The main purpose of the application of the above-mentioned concepts and the pursuit of media education, media literacy, media criticism and media studies today is to understand the process of creating information, its dissemination, commercial, political, economic, spiritual and is to be able to evaluate the information disseminated for cultural purposes while understanding the nature of it.

At the moment, the basics of media education should be included in the curriculum of every educational institution, explaining its basics to students and young people in the educational process in schools in the form of interactive, various games, choosing what is necessary for the growing generation in the intense flow of information. and allows him to be critically evaluated. This, in turn, serves as a basis for the further strengthening of the citizenship position of young people in the future, the ability to objectively assess the events taking place in the world and make the right decisions.

The bottom line is that we all live in a media world and face media literacy challenges every day. It is very important to teach young people the rules of behavior and self-defense in such difficult conditions.

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